

ON THE ROAD TO SUSTAINABILITY: PAVING THE WAY FOR
OPERAS AS AN EFFICIENT OPEN SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HUMANITIES
SCHOLARLY COMMUNICATION RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE

Report on the activities of OPERAS bodies

JANUARY 2024-APRIL 2025

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ON THE ROAD TO SUSTAINABILITY: PAVING THE WAY FOR OPERAS AS AN EFFICIENT OPEN SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HUMANITIES SCHOLARLY COMMUNICATION RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE

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Report in the activities of the OPERAS bodies

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This report describes the activities of each of the tasks in OPERAS-PLUS Work Package 3: Member States and Associated Countries & other OPERAS stakeholders' engagement for the reporting period January 2025 - April 2025 inclusive.

The activities of each stakeholder group have evidenced effective engagement with and involvement of all members of OPERAS community across the different groups and bodies of the infrastructure, including ministry representation.

In order to monitor and assess the quality and efficiency of internal communication channels, coordination bodies and engagement activities, each task has reported on the challenges and lessons learned during the reporting period. In particular the AoC, SIGs and Executive Assembly (EA) have proactively addressed issues resulting from a rapidly growing OPERAS community. Internal communication has been strengthened, and the community has been involved in the process. The Science Advisory Committee (SAC) has also strengthened its connection to the OPERAS community via interaction with SIGs and commenting on OPERAS papers, while remaining an independent body. The General Assembly (GA) has reacted swiftly to the proposal of a Board of Governing Representatives (BGR) by creating new terms of reference and a transitional governance structure in close liaison with the and EA.

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Abstract

This report covers the activities of each of the tasks in OPERAS PLUS Work Package 3: Member States and Associated Countries & other OPERAS stakeholders' engagement for the reporting period January-April 2025 inclusive. In particular, it outlines OPERAS internal support to the Assembly of the Commons (AoC), Special Interest Groups (SIGs), Scientific Advisory Committee (SAC), General Assembly (GA) and Executive Assembly (EA) in order to evidence effective engagement, quality and efficiency of internal communication and the coordination of the different internal groups of OPERAS.

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Glossary

Acronym	Definition
AISBL	Association Internationale Sans But Lucratif (International Non-Profit Association in Belgium)
AoC	OPERAS Assembly of the Commons
BGR	Board of Governing Representatives
COARA	Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment
CO-OPERAS	OPERAS project which addressed the FAIR principles application challenges in the field of Social Sciences and Humanities
DIAMAS	Developing Institutional Open Access Publishing Models to Advance Scholarly Communication Project
DOAS	Diamond Open Access Standard
EA	OPERAS Executive Assembly
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EQSIP	The Extensible Quality Standard for Institutional Publishing developed by DIAMAS
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
ERA	European Research Area
ESFRI	European Strategic Forum on Research Infrastructures
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability
FTE	Full Time Equivalent
GA	OPERAS General Assembly
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
IOAP	Irish Open Access Publishers
KPI	Key Performance Indicator

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MLE	Mutual Learning Exercise
NLP	Natural Language Processing
NN	OPERAS National Nodes. Institutions representing OPERAS AISBL in their respective countries
NUP(s)	New University Presses
OA	Open Access
OAeBU	OA Book Usage Data Trust
OABN	Open Access Books Network
OCT	OPERAS Coordination Team
OIPA	Open Institutional Publishers' Association
OPERAS	OPERAS Scholarly Communication in the European Research Area for Social Sciences and Humanities
OPERAS AISBL	Legal structure incorporated in Belgium and coordinating OPERAS
OPERAS Central Hub	OPERAS AISBL + OCT
OPERAS Core Members	Organisations committing to manage the development of OPERAS are engaged in the Executive Assembly, they are also in charge of the national nodes
OPERAS Ordinary Members	Members of this community committing to participate in OPERAS' activities are engaged in the Assembly of the Commons
OPERAS Research Infrastructure	OPERAS Central Hub + OPERAS National Nodes
OPERAS National Nodes	Institutions representing OPERAS AISBL in their respective countries
OPERAS Supporting Member	European and International infrastructures committing to support the development of OPERAS are engaged in the General Assembly next to the Ministry representatives from the countries represented in the Executive Assembly
PALOMERA	Policy Alignment of Open Access Monographs in the European Research Area Project
POSI	The Principles of Open Scholarly Infrastructure

RI(s)	Research Infrastructure(s)
SAC	Scientific Advisory Committee
SIG(s)	Special Interest Group(s)
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
SSHOC	Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud
TSD	Technical and Scientific Description

Executive summary

This report covers the activities of each of the tasks in OPERAS PLUS Work Package 3: Member States and Associated Countries & other OPERAS stakeholders engagement covering the reporting period January 2024 - April 2025, inclusive.

As part of the ESFRI Roadmap application, OPERAS emphasised the need to grow its membership base across the ERA. This included expansion of Ordinary Members and a particular emphasis on the need to increase core membership from ERA countries in order to increase geographical equity. During the period of this report, six new Ordinary Members were welcomed to the OPERAS community (totalling 47 Ordinary Members). The OPERAS Executive Assembly (EA) also received three new Core Members, which expanded the EA to 13 countries. Furthermore, a new Supporting Member also joined the General Assembly.

As OPERAS grows, so does the need to create efficient and effective lines of communication to ensure that all members get the most out of the OPERAS community and that the OPERAS governance structure continues to work at the optimum level. Therefore, this report outlines OPERAS internal support to the Assembly of the Commons (AoC), Special Interest Groups (SIGs), Scientific Advisory Committee (SAC), General Assembly (GA) and Executive Assembly (EA).

During the reporting period, there were three Assembly of the Commons (AoC) meetings, which achieved a milestone for the project. The first AoC, held in September 2022, presented the OPERAS Strategic Plan to the community. The second meeting in April 2023 focussed on the annual Implementation Plan and invited contributions and feedback from the OPERAS community. During the May 2023 meeting, the SIGs presented their current and planned work and highlighted how their objectives and

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activities are aligned with OPERAS Implementation Plan.

Special Interest Groups (SIGs) comprise the AoC. During the reporting period, the SIG roadmap was introduced as a light touch planning process. As well as detailing SIGs objectives, it also aids the SIGs in aligning their objectives and activities with OPERAS' strategies and ongoing projects, and allows them to better identify their needs and, as a consequence, OPERAS' Coordination Team (OCT) is able to provide better support.

The roadmap and regular coordination meetings have proved to be helpful for SIG coordinators to identify opportunities for collaboration between SIGs and ongoing projects. It has helped as a tool to identify communication needs and other kinds of support.

Mutual Learning Exercises (MLEs) were established alongside the SIG roadmap. Two sessions were organised. Session 1 focused on "How to develop an idea into a new service or a funded project" and was led by the Multilingualism SIG. Session 2 was dedicated to "Ways of creating and engaging a community", led by the Open Access Books Network SIG.

There are two key challenges facing the internal operation of the AoC and SIGs. The first relates to the management of the workload for the SIG coordinators. The coordination meetings, roadmap and mutual learning exercises help in this direction. Furthermore, the practice of co-chairing SIGs is being implemented as standard. The second challenge is to ensure an effective participation of the members, such as regular attendance at meetings, active contribution to the roadmap, and having a proactive attitude. A number of initiatives were introduced by SIGs and these will be further developed during the next reporting period.

The Scientific Advisory Committee (SAC) of OPERAS has been actively engaged in various discussions and planning sessions throughout 2024 and 2025 via monthly online meetings. In summary, the SAC discussed a range of internal processes, strategic collaborations, and technical recommendations in support of OPERAS' objectives and the outcomes of [the Toluca conference](#), and the propositions shared in the Diamond Open Access (OA) discussion paper. A number of external speakers were also invited to various SAC meetings to share their perspectives and projects. In addition an OPERAS's position paper and a SIG white paper were also presented to the SAC for review and comment.

Noteworthy challenges were identified, particularly revolving around the turnover within the SAC. A decision was made to kickstart an open call aimed at candidates

with expertise in specific predefined topics through a gap analysis conducted by SAC members.

The General Assembly (GA), OPERAS' highest decision-making body, discussed a number of issues surrounding the transition of OPERAS to an ERIC. This included the unanimous approval of the creation of a Board of Governing Representatives (BGR). The BGR has a strategic focus on legal, governance, and financial matters related to ERIC establishment. Importantly, the BGR is positioned as an independent and transitional body necessary to foster the building of OPERAS ERIC.

The OPERAS Executive Assembly (EA) comprises core members of OPERAS. During the reporting period, a number of key decisions were taken by the EA. These include: adoption of new OPERAS members, votes on Statutes changes, approval of past and planned budgets and fiscal sponsorship, GA meeting agendas and strategies regarding related discussions with ministries, approval of the OPERAS transition governance model, assessing OPERAS Association Internationale Sans But Lucratif (AISBL) against the Principles of Open Scholarly Infrastructure (POSI), and approval to join various external initiatives.

In response to growing membership of the EA and the wider evolving landscape, a number of improvements have been made to enhance operational efficiency of the EA. This includes general improvement to communications, such as email headers, an internal newsletter and a dashboard giving an overview of pertinent information. Furthermore the EA monthly meeting has been extended to 2.5 hours and follows a more structured approach, which introduces standing items on other OPERAS' bodies in order to ensure effective two-way communication.

This report on the activities of OPERAS bodies is being delivered in month 33 of the project (May 2025). It includes an account of the major activities within the work package tasks covering the second reporting period of the project (January 2024–April 2025). It reflects on the opportunities and perspectives outlined in the previous report. Both reports will feed into the creation of a Dashboard of activities of the OPERAS bodies and assemblies. This will be delivered in the final month of the project (August 2025).

I. Introduction

OPERAS is the Research Infrastructure (RI) supporting open scholarly communication in the social sciences and humanities (SSH) in the European Research Area (ERA). Its mission is to coordinate and federate resources in Europe to efficiently address the scholarly communication needs of European researchers in the field of SSH.

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The OPERAS AISBL was established in 2020 with a working governance model that is closely related to the strategic development of OPERAS as a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC). Building the ERIC implies having Member States at the level of the General Assembly.

As part of the ESFRI Roadmap application, OPERAS emphasised the need to grow its membership base across the ERA. This included expansion of Ordinary Members and a particular emphasis on the need to increase core membership from ERA countries in order to increase geographical equity.

In September 2022, at the start of the OPERAS-PLUS project, OPERAS' ordinary membership stood at 41 with 10 member states (Core Members) and three Supporting Members. As of April 2025, the total has risen to 71.

The OPERAS Executive Assembly also received three new Core members, which expanded the EA to 13 countries.

This resulted in a larger Executive Assembly, an increased membership of OPERAS' SIGs and a growing number of new members to bring up to speed with OPERAS' processes and opportunities.

Membership is expected to increase. As OPERAS grows, so does the need to create efficient and effective lines of communication to ensure that all members get the most out of the OPERAS community and that the OPERAS governance structure continues to work at the optimum level.

Figure 1. OPERAS' membership in the ERA by country.

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1. Ensure an effective engagement with and involvement of all members of OPERAS community across the different groups and bodies of the infrastructure, including ministry representation
2. Monitor and assess the quality and efficiency of internal communication channels, coordination bodies and engagement activities
3. Coordinate the different internal groups of OPERAS, support cross-participation and alignment of their objectives and methods.

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Each task report includes a ‘challenges and lessons learned’ sub-section where issues and opportunities and perspectives are discussed. This allows reflection on the different communication methods required for each stakeholder.

The sections conclude with a number of opportunities and perspectives to take forward. Both this report and the previous one will feed into the creation of a Dashboard of activities of the OPERAS bodies and assemblies, which will be delivered in the final month of the project (August 2025).

II. Governance schema

A. Presentation of the governance

In order to report on the actions taken to promote effective engagement and communication within and between the OPERAS community, it is essential to explain the governance of OPERAS AISBL and the roles of the different internal stakeholders.

The OPERAS AISBL governance scheme manages the different levels of engagement of the different types of stakeholders in the development of the OPERAS Research Infrastructure (OPERAS RI) (Figure 2). The community committing to participate in OPERAS’ activities is engaged as ‘ordinary members’ in the Assembly of the Commons. Organisations committing to manage the development of OPERAS are engaged as Core Members in the Executive Assembly. European and international infrastructures committing to support the development of OPERAS are engaged as ‘supporting members’ in the General Assembly.

Governance Structure

Figure 2. OPERAS Governance Structure

B. Support to the governance: the role of the Coordination Team

The OPERAS Coordination Team (OCT) acts as the Secretariat of OPERAS RI. It is a composite team of employees from OPERAS AISBL and EA members. In both cases, staff hold either permanent contracts or are employed as part of project work.

The OCT provides a variety of different coordination, management and secretariat functions for the OPERAS RI to support and advise the Executive Assembly and the different bodies of OPERAS. It gathers a variety of expertise and knowledge to support the building of OPERAS as an ERIC in areas such as: strategy and policy; legal and financial; community and communication; service management and technical coordination; National Nodes; and project management and planning.

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III. Assembly of the Commons and Special Interest Groups

The [Assembly of the Commons](#) (AoC) is one of OPERAS' governance bodies although it does not have a decisional role. It gathers all Ordinary Members of the infrastructure and it is convened at least once a year. Currently, the objective of the meeting is to present to the Ordinary Members the work completed in the Special Interest Groups over the course of the previous year, propose subjects to be discussed during the General Assembly, and elect the community representatives every two years.

OPERAS [Special Interest Groups](#) (SIGs) work collaboratively, share information, watch, and prepare projects on their topics. Each SIG works under the responsibility of one or more contact points who represent an OPERAS core member. Every ordinary member has to join at least one of the SIGs. In this regard, SIGs serve as an entry door for new OPERAS members. However, any OPERAS member (of any type) can join any SIG and the SIG coordinators can also invite people to participate. This facilitates internal communication flow between the various governance groups within OPERAS.

Internal communication between the various OPERAS groups is key to the development of OPERAS as a mature RI. In the reporting period September 2022 - December 2023, Task 3.1 (Support to the Special Interest Groups and the Assembly of Commons) developed activities aimed at contributing to the achievement of the work package's global objective on internal communication. The OPERAS' community manager leads this task and is responsible for the coordination of both the AoC and SIGs.

To ensure stakeholder engagement of the members at this level, the community manager has organised AoC two meetings, employed a plan of activities for the SIGs (in the form of roadmaps), and continued the development of an activities toolkit for the SIGs through Mutual Learning Exercises. The onboarding meeting to welcome new members and ease their integration into OPERAS activities have become part of standard procedures.

To coordinate and support the participation of the members, the task has contributed to a better alignment between the SIGs activities and OPERAS strategy, as it is executed in its projects. It also contributed to strengthening the connection between AoC and SIGs and other OPERAS boards. It also participated in the efforts to increase OPERAS membership.

These tasks and activities are described in Figure 3 as a number of overlapping objectives. As can be seen, some of the tasks contribute to both ensuring engagement and coordinating activities. Such activities focus on communication and on the alignment between the SIGs and OPERAS national nodes and services. Finally, all these activities are monitored through feedback from the AoC and from the SIGs coordinators.

Figure 3: List of objectives for Task 3.1.

A. Activities

1. Assembly of the Commons

The AoC elects two co-chairs from the Ordinary Members. The chairs have a seat in the General Assembly. Organising regular AoC meetings contributes to increasing the engagement of OPERAS Ordinary Members by informing them of current activities and projects within OPERAS. AoC members are also asked to give input and feedback. The AoC suggestions are presented by the co-chairs to the Executive Assembly (the body responsible for making the decisions).

Meetings

During this reporting period, there were two AoC meetings. The first AoC was a hybrid event in April 2024, during the OPERAS conference in Zadar. This meeting had two

purposes: to present the work of the Special Interest Groups and to present the role of the AoC in OPERAS future governance.

The second AoC meeting was held in October of the same year. On the occasion, the second election of co-chairs took place. Vanessa Proudman from Sparc Europe and Mark Huskisson from PKP were re-elected for a second two-year term. After the election, there was a presentation of [OPERAS Innovation Lab](#) and of the service [Pathfinder](#).

The members participation in the AoC is one of the KPIs of the OPERAS PLUS project and is part of the monitoring activities. Around 50% of the Ordinary Members were represented in the first meeting and 60% in the second one. One of the challenges identified in the previous reporting period was the increase in participation of the members.

2. Special Interest Groups

There were initially seven Special Interest Groups. Now there are six SIGs and three Working Groups. Figure 4 shows the SIGs and their respective coordinators and Figure 5 shows the new organization of the groups and their description. . All the SIGs have their respective page on OPERAS [website](#). These changes will be described later in this report.

Figure 4. OPERAS' Previous Special Interest Groups

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Figure 5. New organization of the Special Interest Groups and Working Groups

In relation to OPERAS' Governance, the Special Interest Groups comprise the Assembly of the Commons. The SIGs are an important part of the OPERAS engine. Due to their nature, the SIGs are the groups capable of identifying needs and challenges coming from the broader community. Such needs and challenges can then be addressed by OPERAS through projects and the development of new services. Finally, the SIGs represent a forum to produce feedback and to assess if OPERAS activities meet the needs of the community. This characteristic is in the heart of the changes in the groups.

a. Roadmap

[The roadmap](#) is a light touch planning tool formally implemented during the course of the OPERAS PLUS project. It is a template for the planning process for SIGs to use

as part of their yearly activities. It gives a framework for the groups while allowing them to maintain their specificities. The SIGs use the roadmap to plan their activities throughout the academic year (from September to July). It is important to note that the roadmap is nonbinding due to the voluntary nature of SIG participation.

The roadmap has two main sections: a general section meant for all the SIGs and a specific one dedicated to each of the groups. The general objectives are based on the list of activities displayed on Figure 3.

The second section is an amalgamation of the completed templates where each SIG presents their objective for the year, describing how this objective aligns with OPERAS' strategies, projects and methods. It is an exercise that helps the SIGs coordinators and participants to clearly identify how their activities are integrated in the OPERAS framework. It also provides the SIGs with the opportunity to track crossovers between the different groups and to identify ways of collaboration. This section also allows SIG coordinators to reflect on any support that might be required from OPERAS bodies, such as the Executive Assembly for strategic issues, the Scientific Advisory Committee for critical comment and open peer review, or from the Communication Officer for the external amplification of results.

A series of quarterly meetings chaired by OPERAS' Community Manager accompany the coordinators of the SIGs in the process of establishing the roadmap, exchanging their experiences, and monitoring the activities. The first meeting was dedicated to a discussion about the new roadmap and the establishment of common objectives of the year. The second and third ones focus on the draft objectives and the development of different activities, such as the organisation of mutual learning exercises (see below) and AoC meetings. The final meeting allows for a moment of informal reflection where the SIGs coordinators can self-assess the work done and identify challenges and opportunities. These SIG coordination meetings are reported to the Executive Assembly.

The practice of having a roadmap has now been established as part of the yearly activities of the SIGs, and of the OPERAS PLUS project. During this reporting period, the SIGs have updated the 2023-2024 version into the third version of the roadmap (2024-2025). Most of the general objectives are unchanged. As the OPERAS community grows, another pressing issue that has to be considered as part of the roadmap is how to ensure participation in the SIGs, whether through increasing engagement of existing members or through bringing new members to OPERAS.

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This reporting period covers two roadmaps. The end of the second roadmap (from 2023 - 2024) and almost the totality of the third roadmap (2024- 2025). The table below shows the evolution of the common objectives in the roadmap.

Table 1: Comparison of common activities carried out by the Special Interest Groups in three years

Objectives	2022 - 2023	2023 - 2024	2024 - 2025
Update the yearly roadmap, including a plan of activities for the Special Interest Groups and taking into account OPERAS Strategic Plan,	x	x	x
Identify communication needs for the Special Interest Groups and establish an articulation with different OPERAS bodies,	x	x	x
Continue the development of a toolbox of activities to be carried out by the Special Interest Groups through Mutual Learning Exercises Think of different topics for the year Include a larger community	x	x	x
Organise at least one Assembly of the Commons	x	x	x
Improve the relations between the SIGs and the Executive Assembly		x	x

Better articulate the work of the SIGs and the National Nodes		x	x
Increase the number of members and engagement of participants		x	x
Prepare a contribution to the OPERAS Conference (Zadar 2024)		x	
Focus on monitoring and assessment			x

Specific activities detailed by the different SIGs in the reporting period January 2024 - March 2025 are described below. It includes the transition from roadmap 2023/2024 to the roadmap 2024/2025 when it is applicable.

Advocacy

In 2023, the SIG started a new strategy of focusing on a single topic per year and inviting experts to work with the SIG members on the chosen topic.

The topic for the academic year 2023/2024 was “responsible research assessment”. The main outcome for the topic was a workshop (“Advocacy for Responsible Research Assessment for the Social Sciences and Humanities”) that the SIG conducted as part of the OPERAS Conference in Zadar, Croatia, on 26 April 2024. In addition, the SIG has published a guide on how to reuse the results of the workshop on Zenodo (see: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11669020>) and has created a blog post (see: <https://operas.hypotheses.org/7395>).

The fact that none of the participants were initially experts on the topic meant there was a lot of work involved to familiarise themselves with the field. In addition, it was difficult to not lose track and keep focusing on concrete advocacy actions instead of the topic itself. It however also gave the SIG the opportunity to create something useful that can be not only reused by the SIG but also by other stakeholders in the future. Additionally, the collaboration with the [GRASP OS Project](#) allowed for a better understanding of OPERAS related activities.

For the academic year 2024/2025 the SIG focuses on Diamond Open Access. Instead of a single event at the end of the year, the SIG continuously develops advocacy actions to help others encompass advocacy on Diamond Open Access in their different realms, especially in the context of the [DIAMAS](#), [PALOMERA](#), and [CRAFT-OA](#) projects.

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As the topic of Diamond Open Access has such a current prevalence, the SIG has decided to also focus on this topic during the next academic year of 2025/2026.

Best Practices

The Best Practices SIG works as a group of experts collaborating with OPERAS projects where topics align and where SIG members can provide valuable expertise and input and possibly with the broader community. The work started in the academic year 2023/2024 and continues in 2024/2025 with the provision of guidance on project deliverables. In the academic year of 2023/2024 the group focused mostly on tasks related to the DIAMAS project and the Diamond Open Access Standard (DOAS).

The group implemented the “News and Newsworthy” activity that can provide content for blog posts or ideas for events about Open Science and Open Access in SSH.

Common Standards and FAIR Principles

The group is working on training OPERAS members on the implementation of FAIR principles by exploring the option of using [FAIR Implementation Profile](#) (FIP) as a methodology, and the [FIP Wizard](#) as a potential tool. The participants of the group were trained on this methodology and respective tool and they are currently working on the criteria to select OPERAS members who will be first to implement the FAIR profiles.

Multilingualism

In the academic years 2023/2024 and 2024/2025 the SIG achieved the objectives related to the development of the collaborative translation platform ([Mondaecus](#)). The group continued the ongoing collaboration related to CoARA WG on Multilingualism and renewed the LINGUA NOSTRA Cost-Action proposal call. The SIG participated in the Mutual Learning Exercise on the topic. There are also some publications related to the work of the group^[1].

Open Access Books Network

From January 2024 until March 2025, the OABN delivered six webinars/events, including: how libraries can evaluate collective funding models for OA books ([recording available via Jisc](#)), how OA associations are supporting OA book publishing ([recording, 66 views](#)), author experiences of publishing an OA book ([recording, 190 views](#)), managing third party materials for OA books ([recording, 154 views](#), and blog forthcoming), looking beyond the end of the PALOMERA project ([blog post](#) and [recording, 91 views](#)), and good metadata practice for OA books (blog post and

recording forthcoming). OABN typically receives between **50-120 attendees** to their events.

The group also started an 'Around the World' blog series, posting a total of six blogs so far with perspectives on OA books from [Italy](#), [Switzerland](#), [Zimbabwe](#), [India](#), [Colombia](#), and an [introductory post](#), with more in the pipeline, including forthcoming posts on Mexico and Sweden. Additionally, they published [11 blogs](#) on various other topics relating to OA books, topics including OA book series (from the perspective of a series editor), updates on the PALOMERA project, OA book business models, and the relevance of equity to our work.

The OABN also participated in two conferences. First, at the OPERAS Conference in Zadar in April 2024, hosting a joint workshop with the OA Business Models WG ([conference schedule](#), Workshop 5). Second, in a panel on equity at the OASPA Conference in Lisbon in September 2024 ([abstract](#), [presentation](#), [recording](#)).

OABN has also set up a quarterly call with three OA book networks: the Open Institutional Publishers' Association (OIPA), the Irish Open Access Publishers (IOAP), and the New University Presses (NUPS) in the Netherlands. This stemmed from the event on OA associations that the SIG held in 2024. It enables the associations to identify areas for collaboration, including a new 'Skillshare' session series where all association members can join an informal call to discuss a topic of interest. The aim is to maximise the effectiveness of all of the associations by encouraging collaboration and knowledge- and resource-sharing.

Open Access Business Models

During the academic year 2023/2024, the group participated in OPERAS Conference in Zadar. The group organized a workshop on OA books definition.

Business Models continues the "News and Newsworthy" activity. It has been giving suggestions of presentations, future projects, collaborations; it is also an opportunity to learn about initiatives in other countries (and published in other languages).

The activities of the group are on hold in 2025 because the coordinator of the group resigned. The Special Interest Group has a new coordination in place, but the activities will resume in the academic year 2025/2026.

Tools and Platforms

The SIG worked on the prototype of an analytical tools catalogue, information cards, and orientation tools based on main potential workflows. That would take the form of

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a wiki¹. Some of the activities included trying to find the best use of the material which the group has made in 2023/2024. However, the group was not able to form a plan as to how to implement the wiki in a way that is both doable, maintainable by the community and also which is not in conflict with other similar services.

In the academic year 2024/2025, the SIG added a new dimension to its work: the group decided to work as a communicator about tools and platforms to the OPERAS community.

The group organised a webinar on AI (AI and LLMs as tools for open scholarly communication in social sciences and humanities) that had about 200 registrations and more than 100 participants. The [recordings](#) are available online. (90 views).

In the beginning of 2025, the coordinators of the Special Interest Group decided to dissolve the group due to the nature of the topic. “Tools and platforms” is too wide as a subject and all the actions seem too big for the SIG, and therefore it was difficult for the group to find concrete topics to focus on. The topic, “Tools and Platforms” can encompass a broad variety of themes and can involve both technical and non-technical issues. One problem might be that the members have different views on what tools and platforms include. As a consequence, it was difficult for the group to decide on the directions to take, and eventually also difficult to keep new members in the group.

Moreover, OPERAS already has the Service and Technology Board and the Innovation Lab which has the overview of the OPERAS tools and platforms. This made it more difficult for the SIG to find its place.

Finally, AI and other kinds of technology are increasingly visible in our society. This development in technology is adding further “problems” to the SIG as its range of topics expands even more.

The roadmap and the regular coordination meetings have proven to be helpful tools as they became not only the place where the SIGs can establish their goals and the methods to achieve them, but also a place for collaboration and reflection. These two management tools allow SIG coordinators to identify similar objectives leading them to work together. By sharing methods employed and actions taken SIG coordinators can indirectly give ideas to the others. Discussions about challenges can lead to collaborative solutions. In other words, this way of managing the SIGs favours crosspollination between the groups.

¹ The prototype is present in the following spreadsheet : https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1WBm-Mm6tveAcglxmP77wK5YE7dxYW_mBAFBC2YQMJMk/edit?gid=1032604805#gid=1032604805
It is available through OPERAS website (<https://operas-eu.org/special-interest-groups/tools-and-platforms/>)

[1] 28 February 2024 (Verkossa, on-line): Delfim Leão & Susanna Fiorini, “OPERAS translation platform”, no âmbito do “DIAMAS Webinar on Multilingualism” [<https://vastuullinentiede.fi/en/news/diamas-webinar-multilingualism-presentations-and-recording>].

April 2024: Launch of the Alpha version of the MONDAECUS platform: www.mondaecus.com

24 April 2024 (Universidade de Zadar): workshop “Pilot Translation Service Platform for Scholarly Production”, Delfim Leão, Nelson Ferreira & Bruno Silva, integrado no OPERAS Conference 2024 - “Opening collaboration for community-driven scholarly communication” [<https://operas-eu.org/news-and-events/calendar-2/operas-conference-2024/>]

8 October 2024 (Lyon – OpenEdition, on-line): Delfim Leão & Nelson Ferreira, “OPERAS translation platform”, regarding “MONDAECUS: *theoria - poiesis - praxis / pensée - production - action*,” as part of “Café Gourmand” organised by OpenEdition.

b. Mutual Learning Exercises

The development of the toolkit of activities continued in the form of Mutual Learning Exercises (MLE). The initial purpose of the MLEs was the exchange between the different SIGs to collectively create solutions and increase the repertoire of methods and strategies of each of the participants.

As this type of activity promotes the construction of new knowledge while facilitating the exchange of information, experiences and lessons learned in practice, within the second roadmap (2023–2024) another MLE session was organised. This was the first session opened up to a larger audience, not limited to SIGs participants.

Session 3 was dedicated to “Multilingualism”. The session was led jointly by the Multilingualism and Open Access Books Network SIGs. The session presented two ways to put multilingualism into practice. The first one was through the use of the OPERAS service Mondaecus, a collaborative translation platform. The text used in the mutual learning exercise were the [Guidelines on Multilingualism](#), produced in the DIAMAS project.

The second example was the ongoing blog series [Around the world with the OANB](#), which consists of bilingual posts representing different OA books communities. This blog series is a response to a survey done by OABN in 2023 in which the community asked for a more international coverage not only based on the English language.

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1. New Special Interest Groups

In the last months there were some changes in the Special Interest Groups.

OA Books Special Interest Groups

New members from OPERAS were interested in creating a new SIG on Open Infrastructure for Open Books. The proposal was to bring together the growing landscape of open, community-led infrastructures that support open access (OA) book publishing. The proposed SIG would develop and support communication channels and engagement between the players in this increasingly complex network, enable growing exchange and interoperability between the different infrastructures, and seed new collaborations, projects and developments, potentially including new OPERAS services, both now and in the future. This group was justified by the fact that this landscape of open and community-led infrastructures, if properly nurtured and connected with each other, has the potential to offer strong and efficient joint solutions to strengthen and develop open access book publishing across Europe and beyond, in ways that respect bibliodiversity and support local publishing cultures.

The idea was well received by the OPERAS Executive Assembly. However, it would mean having three groups that focus on OA books, besides the EA members would need to coordinate another group. Solving this issue represented an opportunity to test a new organization for the SIGs.

A new SIG was created, but it would focus on OA Books and gather the two existing SIGS (OABN and OA Business Models) that would then become Working Groups. Open Infrastructures for Open Books was also created as a Working Group.

The OA Books SIG's main objective is therefore to coordinate meetings and strategic discussions between the three Working Groups. The coordination includes involving the WGs in the preparation of agendas for the Policy Forum for OA Books (hosted by Science Europe in coordination with cOAlition S and OAPEN) and in discussions deriving from the Policy Forum meetings.

The participants of OABN and of OA Business Models were consulted and agreed with the changes. The activities of these two groups remain the same, the change was only in the nomenclature of the groups. The Executive Assembly also agreed with all these changes. The new groups were introduced to the community during a dedicated webinar that gathered about 50 people. An open call was also organised to invite people to join the Open Infrastructure for Open Books Working Groups.

AI Special Interest Groups

At the same time discussions about the dissolution of the Tools and Platform SIG were going on, the growing interest in AI and LLMs became more clear. A new Special

Interest Group on this topic is being prepared. It will be led by two members of the Executive Assembly (CNRS and IBL PAN). The creation of the SIG is yet to be voted by the EA but this decision board has already been informed.

All these changes will be reflected in the roadmap 2025/2026.

3. Engagement and Communication

a. Onboarding new members and engagement

With an expanding membership, there are potential risks to internal engagement as SIGs expand. In order to ensure effective engagement of OPERAS members, the task maintained the procedures for onboarding new members and conducted some follow up actions to maintain engagement. The welcoming meeting helps new members to better understand OPERAS and its activities and favours participation in the different SIGs. The constant involvement of SIGs participants in the roadmap and the acknowledgment of their contribution on SIG pages has been a useful mechanism for encouraging engagement.

b. Communication

Related to work on the SIG web pages and member biographies, new mailing lists were set up for each SIG to facilitate better communication within the different groups. The community is also encouraged to use OPERAS' Mattermost installation for more informal communication and information sharing. SIGs will have their own channels and new channels will be created for the community as required.

Regarding outreach, SIGS and working groups have the support of the OPERAS' communication team for the dissemination of events, publications and other outcomes via the appropriate channels.

B. Challenges and lessons learned

There are two key challenges facing the internal operation of the AoC and SIGs. The first relates to the management of the workload for the SIG coordinators. Core Members offer 0.2 FTE as an in-kind contribution to OPERAS. This includes membership of the EA, attendance at GA and BGR meetings, as well as the coordination of a SIG. As OPERAS membership grows, so do the demands on Core Members' time.

The coordination meetings, roadmap and mutual learning exercises represent some

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help in this direction. Furthermore, the practice of co-chairing SIGs has been implemented to most of the groups. Currently, three of the six SIGs are co-chaired and the new SIG on AI is already establishing a co-leadership. All three working groups are co-chaired.

The second challenge is to ensure an effective participation of the members. This includes regular attendance at meetings, active contribution to the roadmap, and having a proactive attitude. Dealing with broad or new topics is also a challenge for the participants of the different groups. These challenges keep being addressed by the coordinators of the different SIGs and by OPERAS community manager in each new roadmap.

C. Opportunities and perspectives

Changes in the Special Interest Groups are an opportunity to keep the OPERAS engine moving. The SIGs are the privileged place for the community to gather and talk about pressing topics and develop ideas addressing important issues for the broad community. The Open Access Books Network Special Interest Group and its Working Groups as well as the future AI Special Interest Group show how OPERAS listens to the requests of its community.

IV. Scientific Advisory Committee

Notes: SAC meetings/events, recruitment of new members, involvement in other OPERAS activities

The OPERAS [Scientific Advisory Committee](#) (SAC) is an independent body, composed of experts in various aspects of scholarly communication, providing advice and recommendations to the Executive Assembly on the ethical, scientific and technical area for current and future projects as well as OPERAS activities. The SAC was supported throughout 2024-2025 by one of the two co-coordinators of OPERAS for the logistics and communication with the other bodies of OPERAS.

The Scientific Advisory Committee (SAC) of OPERAS has been actively engaged in various discussions and planning sessions since 2022. This section of the report provides a comprehensive overview of the key activities and decisions taken during this period.

A. Activities

This report outlines the principal activities concerning the support provided to the Scientific Advisory Committee (SAC) from January 2024.

In January 2024, the SAC convened to delineate its annual plans, which included the appointment of a committee secretary and the identification of multilingualism-translation and scholarly communication governance as key discussion topics for the year, with position papers to be prepared by the co-chairs. Preparations also commenced for a call to expand the SAC membership by four positions.

February 2024 saw discussions surrounding SAC governance documents and multilingualism topics. The finalization of a call for new SAC members was a significant activity, alongside managing a resignation from the committee.

During March 2024, the call for new SAC members was published, and initial applications were received for review. The SAC also continued its deliberations on two ongoing reports.

No specific SAC support activities were recorded for April 2024 due to meeting cancellations.

In June 2024, new SAC members were successfully onboarded, and the committee contributed to the OPERAS Technical and Scientific Description (TSD). Work progressed on reports concerning multilingualism and Diamond Open Access, and preparations for a new call for an NLP expert were initiated. The SAC's future program was scheduled for discussion in July.

July 2024 involved discussions within the SAC regarding the exploration of use cases and procedures to consolidate its composition, including a process to confirm members' continued engagement and identify potential new candidates.

September 2024 activities included extending the deadline for an NLP specialist application due to a lack of initial responses and scheduling the 2024-25 program. Work commenced on a collective paper addressing the needs of “small journals,” and future meeting topics were outlined,

October 2024 focused on discussions about adding NLP experts to the SAC, with a proposal to onboard two applicants. The committee also reviewed NLP expert applications and progressed on a paper by Jean-Claude Guédon, while initiating collective work on “small journals”.

November 2024 activities included the presentation of the EDCH to the SAC and discussions on a paper concerning OPERAS's infrastructure status. A paper by Jean-Claude Guédon was finalized, and the work on “small journals” continued. The prolonged unavailability of a co-chair was also noted.

By December 2024, the onboarding of new NLP experts was nearing completion. The SAC continued its work on the EDCH presentation, infrastructure discussions, and the “small journals” initiative.

In January 2025, it was reported that the SAC meeting for the month was cancelled due to the coordinator unavailability (off sick). Consequently, a presentation on Pathfinder was rescheduled.

The February 2025 SAC meeting proceeded with a focus on Artificial Intelligence and

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presentations from the GRAPHIA, LUMEN, and FASCA projects.

In March 2025 the SAC discussed VERA and its key challenges, namely low user engagement, inactive projects once initial funding ends, and securing ongoing financial support. Future plans were discussed to boost engagement through features like a pre-project discussion space, improved matchmaking, direct outreach, and exploring strategies like requiring funder-mandated project listings and approaching private foundations for financial backing.

The April 2025 session addressed reforming Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) research evaluation. Current metrics, often STEM-derived, fail to capture SSH's unique outputs and diversity, with English dominance in publishing also a concern. OPERAS aims to lead change by exploring fairer, qualitative methods, new publishing models, and improved peer review. The strategy involves gathering broad feedback to ensure evaluation truly reflects SSH's specific nature.

A discussion on the plan for OPERAS PLUS Task 3.3 – Support to the Scientific Advisory Committee took place in this period and a blueprint was prepared regarding the OPERAS SAC members' engagement strategy.

B. Challenges and lessons learned

At the conclusion of the period, the Committee engaged in a collective reflection regarding the structure and frequency of its meetings. A unanimous consensus emerged to maintain the current approach, consisting of brief one-hour monthly meetings supplemented by an extensive annual face-to-face gathering to accommodate the proceedings of the SAC. Noteworthy challenges were identified, particularly revolving around the turnover within the SAC, as a few junior members withdrew from active participation, primarily attributed to the swift progression of their careers.

Given the need to fill vacant positions within the SAC in 2024, a decision was made to kickstart an open call. The call was explicitly aimed at candidates with expertise in specific predefined topics. Through a gap analysis conducted by SAC members, it was determined that the call for participation should focus on recruiting a researcher in humanities and a researcher in Natural Language Processing (NLP). Additionally, two untargeted positions are slated to be opened alongside these specific roles.

C. Opportunities and perspectives

Based on the lessons learned in 2024-2025, the SAC considered that having a monthly online meeting plus one face-to-face meeting is a good format but requires more assistance from OPERAS AISBL in terms of management and logistics. Since January 2024, an office assistant has been supporting the organisation of the SAC, complementing the ongoing involvement of the co-coordinator..

V. General Assembly

Notes: Meetings, preparation of documents

The General Assembly (GA) is the highest decision-making body and has the powers expressly granted to it by law or by the Articles of Association, in particular the following:

1. Amendments to the Articles of Association
2. Appointment and dismissal of the Statutory Auditor and the fixing of their remuneration
3. Approval of the budget for the following financial year and of the annual accounts, as well as granting discharge to the Executive Assembly, the Secretary-General and the Statutory Auditor
4. Voluntary dissolution of the Association
5. Exclusion of Members.

A. Activities

The General Assembly (GA) is currently composed of EU and international infrastructures that commit to supporting the development of OPERAS, ministries (or proxies) corresponding to the countries where the core members are located, and the Chairs of the AoC, elected by their peers to represent the Ordinary Members at the GA. Members of the OCT attend in a supporting role.

1. Meetings

The General Assembly meets twice a year, a 4-hour virtual meeting and a full-day face-to-face meeting. In case of necessity, extraordinary meetings can take place.

The General Assembly has been chaired by the Secretary-General, following a decision of the General Assembly in 2022. These are the scheduled meetings for the period of this report:

- 29 April 2024 – hybrid
- 25 June 2024 (along with the BGR) – in person
- 20 November 2024 – hybrid
- 27-28 March 2025 (BGR) – hybrid
- 17 June 2025 – hybrid

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2. Topics and activities

The General Assembly serves as the central hub for a diverse range of activities, showcasing a dual nature that encapsulates both formal and dynamic dimensions.

On one hand, the GA engages in the scrutiny of budgets, embodying its role in shaping the financial landscape of the organisation. This formal role underscores the GA's commitment to procedural governance and fiscal responsibility.

On the other hand, the GA is a dynamic forum where scientific inquiry and opportunistic endeavours flourish. It actively participates in the creation of policy briefs, fostering an environment that encourages strategic discussions and innovative problem-solving. The assembly's commitment to addressing challenges is evident in its ability to adapt, demonstrating an opportunist approach to emerging issues.

Finally, the General Assembly serves as a vital consultative body during the crafting of formal documents, adding its expertise and insights to the developmental process, thereby cementing its pivotal role in shaping the organisational narrative.

During the reporting period, following the decision from the Executive Assembly (EA) in May 2023 to move towards an ERIC, the unanimous approval of creating a Board of Governing Representatives (BGR) during the June 2023 General Assembly (GA) signified a pivotal moment. A number of important issues surrounding the transition to an ERIC were discussed by the ministry representatives, these are included in the challenges, opportunities and lessons learned section below.

B. Challenges and lessons learned

In setting up the governance structure of OPERAS, the creation of the EA and GA was an attempt to mirror the structure of an ERIC in order to smooth the transition. However, operational challenges appeared in the current model, particularly the inability of Member State representatives to discuss the creation of the ERIC due to the current composition of the GA.

The GA, recognising challenges in discussing OPERAS ERIC due to its current composition, triggered the Executive Assembly's efforts in crafting a transitional governance structure. This led to the proposal of a new Board of Governing Representatives (BGR) and of a new membership category: the Mandated Organisation, e.g., .On behalf of the United Kingdom, the Department for Science, Innovation and Technology (DSIT) mandates the Arts and Humanities Research

Council (AHRC), a body of UK Research and Innovation (UKRI), to represent the UK in the OPERAS General Assembly.

The GA emerges as a central force in the proposed transition governance model (2024–2027) for OPERAS. This move aims to enhance the alignment between the governance of OPERAS AISBL and the future ERIC governance schema.

OPERAS AISBL's twin goals – supporting ERIC establishment and developing initial services – necessitate sustained operational costs. The BGR, as outlined in the draft Terms of References, has a strategic focus on legal, governance, and financial matters related to ERIC establishment. Importantly, the BGR is positioned as an independent and transitional body necessary to foster the building of OPERAS ERIC, but not strictly tied to the governance of OPERAS AISBL.

C. Opportunities and perspectives

The proposed creation of a new membership category, Mandated Organisation, underscores the GA's role in aligning strategies between the BGR and OPERAS AISBL. The GA's composition will now include chairs of the Assembly of the Commons (AoC), the Supporting Members, and the Mandated Organisations. The dynamic inclusion of diverse entities emphasises the GA's central role in shaping the association's direction. The GA's responsibility in overseeing the preparation of documents for the BGR and examining hypotheses underscores its strategic importance. The smooth and transparent dialogue between the GA and the BGR is crucial and will be supported both by the EA and the OPERAS Coordination Team (OCT).

The creation of the BGR stems from a proposal by the French Ministry, with France envisioned as the host country for OPERAS ERIC. The GA's step-by-step approach, involving votes on the BGR's creation and Mandated Organisation status, highlights the GA's careful consideration in the transition process. The addition of Mandated Organisation membership signifies the GA's commitment to maintaining quality and aligning OPERAS' development with member states' needs.

To prepare for the creation of the ERIC, OPERAS aims to shift from project-dependent funding to a more sustainable financial model. The introduction of mandated organisation status involves national contributions based on a country's GDP. This strategic move underlines the GA's role in steering OPERAS towards a more sustainable and solid development phase, contributing to the long-term sustainability of the Research Infrastructure. The GA's central position is pivotal in shaping both the governance and financial aspects of OPERAS.

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VI. Executive Assembly

A. 2025 main highlights

The Executive Assembly (EA) assumes a pivotal administrative role in steering the strategy and development of the AISBL, overseeing crucial aspects such as accounting, statutes, and membership matters. It serves as the primary entity engaged in the ERIC process, playing a key role in both the preparation of relevant documents and interactions with governmental ministries. Furthermore, the EA holds responsibility for the comprehensive management of the Research Infrastructure, including but not limited to funded projects, Special Interest Groups, National Nodes, the Scientific Advisory Committee (SAC), and various services.

The OPERAS EA comprises organisations that have successfully applied to become Core Members of OPERAS. These organisations have a heightened commitment to the advancement of OPERAS. The EA has an executive role while the OCT is supposed to implement the decisions of the EA. It is constituted by the administrators of the Association who, in turn, present the tasks and accomplishments undertaken to the General Assembly.

Beyond the regular agenda items, such as the COARA action plan, the creation of new Special Interest Groups (SIGs), Scientific Advisory Committee (SAC) membership, OPERAS' relationship with the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), the development of the Diamond Open Access model, the Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud (SSHOC), budget adoption, membership in the European Alliance for Social Sciences and Humanities (EASSH), and the strategic direction for future funding calls, the EA has focused on managing three specific challenges in recent months. These challenges, which will be discussed in detail in this report, are: 1) the building of the future European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC), 2) the reorganisation of the Executive Assembly to streamline operations and address the growing workload, and 3) its role in the preparation of the General Assembly and the Board of Governing Representatives.

1. Preparing the building of the future ERIC

1. OPERAS ERIC governance model

In preparation for the establishment of OPERAS ERIC, significant efforts have been made to define its governance structure. Two workshops were organised in collaboration with DARIAH, OPERAS' supporting partner, and the Arts and Humanities ERIC, to guide OPERAS in developing a governance model tailored to its needs. DARIAH produced a comprehensive report summarising the outcomes of these

workshops, titled *Report on OPERAS-DARIAH Governance Model Workshops*: [Report OPERAS-DARIAH workshops: governance model OPERAS ERIC](#).

A key principle that emerged from these discussions is the importance of maintaining the strong involvement of the OPERAS community within the governance of the ERIC. Although the proposed governance model includes a variety of committees, adding some complexity, it is a reflection of OPERAS' current organisational structure and ensures continuity and representation from across the network.

2. TSD writing and adoption

[OPERAS technical and scientific description \(TSD\): CURRENT VERSION](#)

The OPERAS Technical and Scientific Description (TSD) is a critical document for the ERIC application, alongside the Statutes. The TSD, currently in draft form, has been primarily prepared by the OPERAS Coordination Team (OCT). However, members of the Executive Assembly have been actively encouraged to contribute to and discuss its contents before final approval. This collaborative feedback loop ensures that the document fully reflects the ambitions and needs of OPERAS, and it will be presented for final approval to both the General Assembly (GA) and the Board of Governing Representatives (BGR) in June 2025.

3. Renewal of the coordinators to ensure continuity until the ERIC building:

To ensure the continuity of leadership during the ERIC's formation phase, the Executive Assembly voted unanimously in September 2024 to renew the mandates of the coordinators until 2028, or until the ERIC is officially established, whichever comes first. The resolution stipulates that "the coordinators are appointed for a term of four financial years, ending on 31 December 2028, or until their mandate is revoked by the Executive Assembly or the creation of OPERAS ERIC." The Executive Assembly delegated the implementation of this decision to the Secretary General, ensuring a smooth leadership transition throughout the ERIC-building process.

2. Discussing the organisation of the EA to better manage OPERAS while addressing overload

A questionnaire has been prepared within the partners of the WP3 to understand how each EA member positions himself or herself as an individual regarding the different duties of an EA member.

The objectives were several:

- a) Defining whether EA members feel being not enough involved or too much in some topics - especially to address potential overload commitment

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- b) Addressing the roles of EA members and ordinary members in order to assign some responsibilities to EA and/or ordinary members
- c) The usage of EA members skills and interests to work in smaller groups on strategic issues

The results have been presented to the EA members with two objectives: 1) identifying what can be improved during the AISBL lifetime; 2) preparing the perimeter of the future Strategic Committee that is supposed to replace the EA in the ERIC.

Do you wish to be more involved in OPERAS activities?

13 réponses

Can you rank the activities in which you, on a personal aspect, are involved as an EA member? From what you think could be reduced to what you think should be increased or is particularly strategic?

Do you think other individuals within your organisation could support the areas that were not prioritised?

12 réponses

Do you think other OPERAS members can do the work in the activities that were not prioritised?

12 réponses

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The results of the questionnaire are very satisfying for different reasons:

1. The EA members have shown a strong commitment and a willingness to pursue this commitment.
2. The EA members are open to give more room to ordinary members in managing specific activities that are under their responsibility.

These results have been extensively discussed within the EA to see how to move on. For instance, the involvement of ordinary members is organised and represented in the governance scheme. However as the ERIC should be built in 2027 and the governance model will be adapted, the main suggestion is to not put too many changes but more to open slowly and depending on opportunities the possibilities for members to rely more on other colleagues in their own institution or with ordinary members' representatives.

In order to discuss the ERIC's role and organisation more in depth, the EA members have convened in a face-to-face meeting on 5-6 May 2025. The conclusions of the meeting have shown the EA members are ready to share responsibilities within their own organisation but also with ordinary members, especially related to the SIGs management. The next step consists in identifying ways of involving members into specific tasks.

3. Preparing the GA and BGR meetings with the funding needs in perspective

The EA assumes a pivotal administrative role in steering the strategy and development of the AISBL, overseeing crucial aspects such as accounting, statutes,

and membership matters. It serves as the primary entity engaged in the ERIC process, playing a key role in both the preparation of relevant documents and interactions with governmental ministries. Furthermore, the EA holds responsibility for the comprehensive management of the Research Infrastructure, including but not limited to funded projects, Special Interest Groups, National Nodes, the Scientific Advisory Committee (SAC), and various services.

B. Opportunities and perspectives

Based on the identified challenges, a set of strategic decisions have been formulated to enhance the effectiveness and strategic focus of the Executive Assembly:

1. Preserving the Influential Role of the EA

- Efforts will be made to uphold and strengthen the pivotal role of the EA as a potent governing body for the RI. This will involve ensuring that the EA retains its influential position in guiding the strategic direction of OPERAS

2. Fostering Consensus and Trust Among EA Members

- A concerted emphasis will be placed on maintaining a collaborative and trustful atmosphere within the EA. It is imperative to encourage EA members to continue working together in a consensus-driven manner, fostering a collective and unified approach to decision-making.

3. Simplifying Procedures for EA Members

- To alleviate potential complexities, a commitment will be made to avoid unnecessary procedural intricacies for EA members. Streamlining processes will contribute to a more efficient and agile decision-making framework

4. Enhancing the Strategic Focus of the EA

- A shift toward a more strategic orientation for the EA will be actively pursued. The focus will be redirected from daily operational activities (which will be shifted and allocated to the OCT) to high-level strategic considerations, ensuring that the EA's efforts align with overarching organisational goals

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5. Maintaining Face-to-Face Meetings and Open Discussions

- Recognizing the value of direct interaction, regular face-to-face meetings will be preserved as a fundamental aspect of EA engagement. Open discussions will be encouraged to promote a collaborative exchange of ideas and insights

6. Establishing Task Forces (TFs) for Specific Topics:

- Task Forces (TFs) will be established to address specific topics such as POSI principles, briefing papers, [EOSC](#) tasks, [COARA](#), etc. These TFs, comprising 2-3 EA members, may collaborate with or without the support of an OCT member. These short-term TFs will be dedicated to non-high strategic topics, with a defined duration to discuss and prepare documents for sharing with the EA members. The goal is to provide well-informed suggestions for decisions or actions, particularly in areas not directly related to administrative, financial, or legal matters

These strategic decisions present the opportunity to reinforce the EA's efficacy, strategic focus, and collaborative ethos, contributing to the continuous improvement of OPERAS' governance structure.

VII. Conclusion

This report describes the activities of each of the tasks in OPERAS-PLUS Work Package 3: Member States and Associated Countries & other OPERAS stakeholders' engagement for the reporting period January 2024-April 2025 inclusive.

The activities of each stakeholder group have evidenced effective engagement with and involvement of all members of OPERAS community across the different groups and bodies of the infrastructure, including ministry representation.

In order to monitor and assess the quality and efficiency of internal communication channels, coordination bodies and engagement activities, each task has reported on the challenges and lessons learned during the reporting period. In particular the AoC, SIGs and EA have proactively addressed issues resulting from a rapidly growing OPERAS community. Internal communication has been strengthened, and the community has been involved in the process. The SAC has also strengthened its

connection to the OPERAS community via interaction with SIGs and commenting on OPERAS papers, while remaining an independent body. The GA has reacted swiftly to the proposal of a BGR by creating new terms of reference and a transitional governance structure in close liaison with the GA and EA.

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